

Design education and practice: Interior design education and its evolution.
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Abstract:

The interior design profession dates back to early history, when shelters existed to provide the interior spaces that offered comfort to their inhabitants. Those spaces influenced the lives of their occupants in a significant way. Buildings and their interiors are placed to serve the purpose and styles of the lives and distinctively of their origins.

The profession of interior design is a fast-growing profession worldwide with challenges to address the artistic, intellectual, innovative and applied considerations necessary to create an environment for human comfort. It is the field with interweaving boundaries and for this reason, Interior design education has progressed historically under a variety of academic fields, from construction, architecture, arts and crafts, etc.

The emergence of interior design as a separate profession and practice is a relatively new development. Therefore, the process of formalisation and firm rooting of the profession is still in its initial stages. This paper aims to present the various landmark events that led to the consolidation of this profession and tends to give a brief overview of the struggle of this discipline both in terms of profession and academia to create its significant identity.

This paper attempts to explore the evolution of the discipline from varied short courses to full time degree programs of interior design. The last part of the paper attempts to put in perspective the evolution and maturing of interior design profession and practice in Pakistan.

The essence of interior design will always be about people and how they live. It is about the realities of what makes for an attractive, civilised, meaningful environment, not about fashion or what's in or what's out. This is not an easy job
 -Albert Hadley

Research objectives: To investigate the impacts of landmark events on the development of the interior design profession.

Research questions: What are the challenges faced by the interior design profession/practice in Pakistan?

Introduction:

Design education has evolved over the past years from being a mere function of styling or aesthetics (where form and function are the focus) to design as a process (where design thinking is integrated into the development process). Today, it has become a strategic element and an innovation leading process. Design can transform the way we do things and result in new economic benefits and a better quality of life. The strategic nature of design helps solve problems in ways that are functionally and aesthetically pleasing and make economic sense.

Similarly is the case is with interior design education, it evolved from the concept of mere surface décor and aesthetics to an instinctive part of the building process, which caters to the internal environment of the building, which is relatively different to the principles of the traditional educational approach. Interior design was taught in the early years from decorating programs to art school, to programs of home economics and architecture. Therefore, it is a multifaceted discipline that emerged from a wide variety of educational methods and contexts. These many methods of early interior design education illustrate the complex historical process through which the profession reaches its identity.

Figure 1: Timeline of Interior Design.

When the emergence and development process of “interior design” is examined, it is seen that the idea of “use of space” dates back to ancient times. Throughout the history of civilisation, the practices of “using interior space” have progressed sometimes in collaboration with architecture and sometimes free from its influence. Therefore, interior design is considered the extension of an influential tradition of “using space”. However, the development of interior design as a profession reveals that it was initiated and institutionalised in the United States, the country which is characterised by the first practical applications, the first professionals and the first educational programs of the field. Later, this process spread to other countries all over the world. (Interior architecture)¹

Interior design profession evolution:

The doors for the profession of interior design opened at the turn of the twentieth century for various reasons. One of the main reasons was the technical advancements during the nineteenth century that paved the way for machine made furnishings and products. This exposure to new products resulted in a new interest being developed in interior decoration.

Figure.2: From Interior decoration to Interior Design and architecture.

Historians credit Elsie de Wolfe (1865-1950) of the USA as the first professional to successfully engage in interior decoration as a separate career from architecture. She established a career by offering “**interior decoration**” services to her social circle in New York City. She developed a new approach by combining interior decoration practices with building, drawing and design methods of architecture. The first step of this approach was to determine the requirements, demands and likes of the customers. Later, she chose the furniture, fabric, colour and ornaments according to these criteria and finally drew a suitable project on a piece of paper and put the design into practice accordingly.²

In professional terms, Wolfe’s approach set the ground for the study methods in the field of interior design during the early 1900s. Moreover, she radically changed the design conception of the period. She became the pioneer in the development of a new interior design mentality as her famous quotation below implies: “**I opened the doors of American House and the windows and let in the air and the sunshine**”.³

Even well-known architects as Ludwig Mies Van Der Rohe, F.L. Wright, and Louis I.Khan not only carried forward architectural design but also impacted the concepts of interior spaces. The works of Wright contributed a lot to the development of architecture and the formation of a modern interior design in the United States. For Wright, “space is a single and flowing entity and it serves its primary purpose with its ornaments, technology and the materials used”. Just like Wolfe, Wright also did his best to be involved in every phase of his design and application process to be able to achieve a successful outcome. In addition, he reflected his unique design approach on his works ranging from furniture, fireplaces, and stained-glass Windows, illuminants and even statues. He tried to redirect the attention from architecture to life in interiors, which is an outcome of modern life, by uttering the following sentence: “Space within becomes the reality of the building”.⁴

The most prominent development of the interior design profession was after World War II. Interior design courses were established with the publication of textbooks and reference sources. Historical accounts of interior designers and firms distinct from the decorative arts specialists were made available. Organisations to regulate education, qualifications, standards and practices. They were later established for the profession.

**PRE - INDUSTRIAL
REVOLUTION**

**POST - INDUSTRIAL
REVOLUTION**

**MODERN &
CONTEMPORARY**

Figure 3: Development of styles in Interior Design

In the **1950s**, with the expansion of commercial properties in the USA, interior design became a separate field from interior decoration and architecture. The term “interior design” first appeared as it departed from the American Institute of Decorators (AID) and the founding **National Society for Interior Designers (NSID)** in 1957, since “decoration” was no longer able to completely include the professional works that interior design demands. This was the first time interior design was formally placed on the platform of a professional organisation.⁵

In **1970s** were marked as an era for the **professionalisation** of interior design. The establishment of a nationwide examination by the National Council for Interior Design Qualifications (NCIDQ) and accreditation of educational programs by the Foundation for Interior Design Education and Research (FIDER). This movement towards professionalisation was reinforced by the publication of books on the subject. By the **1980s**, architecture firms realised the potential of this new market and began to hire interior designers and added interior design to their list of services.⁶

Interior design was previously seen as playing a secondary role to architecture. It also has many connections to other design disciplines, involving the work of architects, industrial designers, engineers, builders, craftsmen, etc. For these reasons, the government of interior design standards and qualifications was often incorporated into other professional organisations that involved design. Organisations such as the Chartered Society of Designers, established in the UK in 1986, and the American Designers Institute, founded in 1938, were established as organisations that governed various areas of design and specific representation for the interior design profession was developed.⁷

In the first quarter of the 20th century, two different professional conceptions emerged as a result of two different approaches adopted towards the interior profession; namely, Interior Design and Interior Architecture, which is the result of the development of interior design research and pedagogy. These two concepts have affected both professional and educational practices and opened a new debate for the profession.⁸

Professionalization of Interior Design Presentation - Time Line

1878	First semi-annual furniture market (held in Grand Rapids, Michigan).
1904	First documented use of term "interior decoration." First courses in interior decoration offered at the New York School of Applied and Fine Arts (Now Parsons).
1905	Elsie de Wolfe obtains her first commission as an interior decorator, and is identified as being the first interior decorator.
1925	Dorothy Draper starts the "Architectural Clearing House" and is identified as the first woman interior decorator to specialize in commercial interiors.
1931	The American Institute of Interior Decorators (AIID) is formed.
1936	AIID changes its name to the American Institute of Decorators (AID).
1957	National Society for Interior Designers (NSID) is formed as a splinter group of the New York Chapter of the AID.
1961	AID changes its name to the American Institute of Interior Designers (still AID).
1963	National Office Furnishings Association (NOFA) creates NOFA-d (NOFA designers), a professional group for Interior Designers.
1969	Institute of Business Designers (IBD) was started from NOFA-d (name changed from NOFA-d).
1970	Foundation for Interior Design Education Research (FIDER) is formed to review and accredit undergraduate and graduate interior design programs.
1974	National Council for Interior Design Qualification (NCIDQ) is formed to develop and administer a national interior design qualification exam.
1975	American Society of Interior Designers (ASID) is created from the union of American Institute of Interior Designers (AID) and National Society of Interior Designers (NSID).
1982	Alabama becomes first state with title registration legislation for Interior Design.
1992	Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) becomes law, identifying accessibility standards for all public buildings.
1994	Unification of International Business Designers (IBD), International Society of Interior Designers (ISID), and Council of Federal Interior Designers (CFID) to form International Interior Design Association (IIDA), with the intent to create an international association with a united mission that would represent interior designers worldwide.
2006	Foundation for Interior Design Education Research (FIDER) becomes the Council for Interior Design Accreditation (CIDA).

Figure 4: Professionalisation of Interior Design.

Interior design Education evolution:

The history of interior design education as a professional degree program carved its path early when the design schools were established. Design education is a complex field in which several theories, paradigms, ideas, principles, conventions and clichés prevail. (Gurel, 2004. P. 193). In addition to theory, form and function, design education is composed of several components, like art, technology, drafting, rendering, model making and computer software are used to bring creative ideas to reality. These methods of developing and creativity began a hundred years ago and have progressed into what we know as today's design education.

Early known architecture and design schools such as **École des Arts** are credited for the origins of the studio model and design jury (Gurel, 2004). Bauhaus was established in 1919 by École des Beaux Arts graduate Walter Gropius. It was another important design school which carved the path for interior design education and began to introduce textiles and furniture design in architecture schools. The integration established an understanding that Interior design is a separate and important entity in design education, and Interior design concepts were established through theory and discourse. ⁹

Frank Aluah Parsons is credited for developing the first Interior design program in the USA, which is known as the Parsons School of Design NYC (Parsons 2008). The school's first program of interior design started in 1930. Interior design programs were established in design and art schools till recent times they separated from decorating art. The University of Oklahoma moved its interior design program from the College of Human Environmental Science to the College of Architecture in 1982. (Kendrix 2008). The advancement in technology in the last few decades has allowed the design profession to grow tremendously, and what we see now is a profession which is based on a multi-faced approach, bridging ties with many related fields.

“From interior decorating, which mainly involved the furnishing and decorating of existing spaces, programs of interior design evolved to encompass the study of complex design processes, various behavioural theories and the creation of new spaces. Curricula for interior design education developed from three primary academic areas: (1) as an outgrowth of the fine and decorative arts, (2) as a component of home economics and (3) as a specialised

focus in architecture... Each provides a slightly different focus, yet contains the necessary elements required for a Professional interior design program”

It is believed that the ideological development leading to the transformation from “decoration” to “design” has played a significant role in the dilemma between interior design and interior architecture, which has been a topic of discussion since the first half of the 20th century. However, the main problem is the subtlety of its borderline with architecture, which sparked considerable reactions in the field. Therefore, the **United States Department of Education Institute of Education Sciences** felt the need to define the terms related to interior design and interior architecture.¹⁰

Program Area	Title and Code	
Visual and Performing Arts	Instructional programs that focus on the creation and interpretation of works and performances that use auditory, kinesthetic and visual phenomena to express ideas and emotions in various forms, subject to aesthetic criteria.	<p>Interior Design</p> <p>A program in the applied visual arts that prepares individuals to apply artistic principles and techniques to the professional planning, designing, equipping and furnishing residential and commercial interior spaces. Includes instruction in computer applications drafting and graphic techniques; principles of interior lighting, acoustics, systems integration and color coordination; furniture and furnishings; textiles and their finishing; the history of interior design and period styles; basic structural design; building codes and inspection regulations; and applications to office, hotel, factory, restaurant and housing design.</p>
Architecture and Related Services	Instructional programs that prepare individuals for professional practice in the various architecture-related fields and focus on the study of related aesthetic and socioeconomic aspects of the built environment.	<p>Interior Architecture</p> <p>A program that prepares individuals to apply architectural principles in the design of structural interiors for living, recreational and business purposes and to function as professional interior architects. Includes instruction in architecture, structural systems design, heating and cooling systems, occupational and safety standards, interior design, specific end-use applications and professional responsibilities and standards.</p>

Figure.5: Program areas in Interior Design

Interior Design Model – Case of Bauhaus School of Art and Design, Germany:

This program offers applied visual art that prepares individuals to apply artistic principles and techniques to the professional planning, designing, equipping and furnishing of residential and commercial interior spaces. It includes instruction in computer applications drafting and graphic techniques; principles of interior lighting, acoustics, systems integration and color coordination; furniture and furnishings; textiles and their finishing; the history of interior design and period styles; basic structural design; building codes and inspection regulations; and applications to office, hotel, factory, restaurant and housing design.¹¹

Interior Architecture Model - Case of Parsons School, NYC:

This program prepares individuals to apply architectural principles in the design of structural interiors for living, recreational and business purposes and to function as professional interior architects. It includes instruction in architecture, structural systems design, heating and cooling systems, occupational and safety standards, interior design, specific end-use applications and professional responsibilities and standards.¹²

The Distinction was formally cleared after the establishment of the American Society of Interior Designers (ASID). However, the definitions offered did not bring solutions to the problems regarding education and profession. This situation was discussed during a roundtable session in 2009. Fellows Forum at the IDEC International Conference held in St. Louis, the United States. At the end of this conversation following points were made.

- Interior design becomes licensed in all states and is identified as the sole profession dealing specifically with the interior environment. A collaborative design community flourishes between architects and interior designers.
- Interior design is one of the several terms used to identify professionals working within the interior environment. Others include interior architects, inter-space designers, etc. Routes to the practice are diverse and include, but are not limited to, passage of the National Council for Interior Design Qualification or National Council of Architectural Registration Boards exams.
- Interior architecture becomes the accepted term globally for those working with interiors. Interior architects are required to graduate from a Council for Interior Design Accreditation-accredited program and take the National Council for Interior Design Qualification exams.
- There is a split in the profession, with those focusing on residential design retaining the right to call themselves ‘interior designers’ and those with a commercially based practice addressing health, safety and welfare issues adopting the term ‘interior architect’.¹³

The interior architecture relationship with art, design and architecture:

Relation to design:

Interior architecture has several dimensions, depending on the standpoint one takes. To simplify, it can be understood as show in the figure below.

As a body of knowledge, it can be defined list of subjects that is gathered into six knowledge areas:

1. Human Environment Needs
2. Design
3. Product and Materials
4. Interior Construction, Codes & Regulations
5. Communication
6. Professional Practice¹⁴

Figure.6: Interior Design relation with art, design and architecture.

What is significant in the illustration shown above is that the areas are interconnected. As professionals, most interior architects view the field not as separate areas, but as areas intertwined. The interconnection consists of six distinct areas of knowledge, and each of them includes a number of subjects, which strongly inform us that many professions correlate with Interior Design.¹⁵

Figure.7: Interconnectivity in Interior Design

Case of Pakistan:

In Pakistan, Interior design or interior architecture design is still confused with interior decoration. In reality, the subject of Interior design covers knowledge of architecture, fine arts, science and engineering. It demands command over important issues like internal climate control, illumination engineering, fire safety, security, space planning, comfort and aesthetics, etc. The subject of decoration, which is a small part of the Interior design, covers surface treatments, colour coordination and soft furnishing.

In the context of Pakistan, architects usually create and design the building structures and design the interiors as well. They would most often engage craftsmen to produce the desired furnishings and complete the interior. The architectural schools barely touch upon the subject of interior design, and do not do justice to the subject of interior design. The industry of architecture has made its foundation in the form of PCATP (Pakistan Council of Architects and Town Planners), established by the government; on the contrary, the interior design has no such regulatory body that could safeguard the profession in Pakistan. There has been an initiative by Danish Azar Zubay, the most senior interior designer, in the form of PIID (Pakistan Institute of Interior Designers), but it has not achieved a similar status to PCATP.¹⁶

The profession still struggles to make its distinct identity in the context of Pakistan because of the non-existence of a constitutionally established governing body that can recognise interior design as a profession and can monitor design standards, look into the accreditation of curriculum offered through various interior design programs all around the country.

There exists a massive niche for more interior design schools in our context, which can deliver in-depth, precise education and do justice to the interior design profession. The various schools that do exist in Pakistan have developed **models** of their own, some would offer programs inclined towards interior architecture, others would offer programs inclined towards interior decoration. This confusion would not be cleared unless a regulatory body offered an accreditation system and gave a set of guidelines to these institutes to follow, as set by the American system of accreditation.

The interior design department at the Indus Valley School of Art and Architecture is the only bachelor's degree program in Pakistan which is placed within the department of architecture and the only school catering to the concept of interior architecture. Based on the guidelines developed by **PIID** and **AIID**, this program is envisioned to make its own identity by grounding contextual knowledge of arts, crafts, architecture and details as compared to internationally inspired interiors. Our region is abundantly rich in the arts, crafts and architecture that constantly remind us of our glorious past, but we see no inspirations and translations of these treasures into the interior practice in Pakistan. One of the reasons is that the profession of interior design in Pakistan has a relatively short history as compared to the rest of the world.

Thus, we need to understand in our education paradigm that both architecture and interiors are based on similar education models, the only difference is in the **scale and detail**. (Two Danish researchers once wrote that the users of architecture should be animated to discover the difference in sensuous feeling that arises between forms and colour, texture and the changes in materials, and variations of space and light as we move through the architecture. To interior architecture, these "sensuous encounters" are fundamental to the design. The term "sensuous encounters" relates twofold – on one hand, it relates to architecture, the physical environment with its elements of materials, light and colours. On the other hand, it relates to the abstract space – the atmosphere of a place and the storytelling - the space where the story takes place. Both of these aspects deal with the user's perception of the environment, how one experiences a place, both physically but also mentally.)¹⁷ And these aspects of architecture are essential to interior architecture. It can be said that interior architecture and architecture are intertwined - it is the inside and the outside, the subjective and the objective experience of the same physical environment. Hence, our education needs to focus towards an extensive and inclusive architectural/interior profession that recognises **disciplinary speciality** as a complement to core knowledge.

Conclusion:

The image of an Interior Designer has changed dramatically from the early 1900s description of individuals with no formal training in design, who approached design with an intuitive flair coupled with social connections. The interior design profession has seen many changes in the last 70 years, including creating professional organisations, changing the name, developing a code of ethics, establishing educational requirements, implementing a comprehensive examination, and working towards legal regulation.

"Between architecture and interior architecture, there is a difference in focus and scale" (Brian Lawson).

As beautifully said by **Brian Lawson in the above-mentioned quote**, it is time for the architecture and interior design profession to make this a priority. It is time to give serious attention to the idea of an expanded and inclusive educational model, a model that allows both architecture and interior to share knowledge reflective of our contemporary practices. Many of the best academic programs in the country are asking for it. A more inclusive, diverse and unified profession is needed in education and practice. One can only imagine how such a re-envisioned profession might impact our collective potential and influence in the world.

Appendix

The following definitions were taken from the U.S. Department of Education, Institute of Education Sciences.

Interior Architecture:

Interior Architecture is an instructional program that prepares individuals for the independent professional practice of interior architecture. The processes and techniques of designing living, work and leisure indoor environments as integral components of a building system are involved. It includes instruction in building design and structural systems, heating and cooling systems, safety and health standards, and interior design principles and standards.

Definition listed under “Architecture and related services” at <http://nces.ed.gov/pubs2002/cip2000/ciplist90.Asp?CIP2=04>

Interior design is defined as the art and science of enhancing the interiors, sometimes including the exterior, of a space or building, to achieve a healthier and more aesthetically pleasing environment for the end user. An interior designer is someone who plans, researches, coordinates, and manages such projects. Interior design is a multifaceted profession that includes conceptual development, space planning, site inspections, programming, research, communicating with the stakeholders of a project, construction management, and execution of the design.

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